

Shaking Hands with Common Foes: Clique premium and Information Diffusion in Private Equity Networks*

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Abstract

The fastest growing segment of private equity deals is secondary buyouts (SBOs) sales from one private equity (PE) firm to another. We operationalize a novel *FactSet* database to map the network structures of secondary buyouts between PE firms. We offer three contributions. First, after controlling for economic covariates, we find that PE firms are almost three times more likely to transact if they share a partner, that is both firms belong to the same clique. Second, we find that the profitability of such transactions is unambiguously higher relative to the baseline only if these are the result of repeated interaction between firms belonging to the same cliques. In other words, a *clique premium* exists under repeated interaction. Third, we provide evidence that the economic incentive at the core of clique premium may be related to access to information. In fact, we show that information related to transactions diffuses through the network, with 23% and 16% of the information going one and two steps beyond transacting parties, respectively.

Keywords: Private Equity, Secondary Buyouts, Networks, Information Diffusion, ERGMs, Network Formation, Financial Networks, SBOs, Clique Premium, Contagion.

JEL Classification: G23, G24, G32.

*Email: ag2051@cam.ac.uk. Institute of Criminology, Sidgwick Avenue Cambridge CB3 9DA. This research is supported by the EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme through Marie Skłodowska-Curie Project 101022681, the Australian Research Council through Discovery Project DP170100429 and BPN grant 2031. Declaration of Interest: None. The authors are particularly indebted to the Editor B.M. Lucey and two anonymous referees for extremely valuable suggestions. We would also like to thank Mikhail Anufriev, Hardy Hulley, Justin Lal, Jamie Olsen, Kenny Phua, Talis Putnins, Valentyn Panchenko and participants of seminar at University of Technology Sydney, AMES2019 and CMES2019 for useful comments.